

UNDERSTANDING AND COMPETENCY OF NURSES IN APGAR SCORING IN NEONATAL CRITICAL CARE

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: The APGAR score is a standardized tool used to rapidly assess a newborn's clinical condition immediately after birth and to guide the need for resuscitation. Despite its widespread use, gaps in nurses' knowledge and interpretation of low scores can impact neonatal outcomes. This study aimed to evaluate the knowledge and competence of nurses regarding APGAR scoring in nurseries and Neonatal Intensive Care Units (NICU) of tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar.

METHODS: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted from July to September 2025 in Khyber Teaching Hospital and Lady Reading Hospital. A total of 60 nurses with at least six months of neonatal or pediatric experience participated. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire assessing general knowledge of the APGAR score, its timing, purpose, and the scoring of individual parameters: respiration, heart rate, muscle tone, reflex response, and skin color. Descriptive statistics were analyzed using SPSS.

RESULTS: Most participants were female (80%) and worked in the NICU (60%). Forty percent of nurses correctly identified an APGAR score of 2 at 1 minute as severe asphyxia requiring immediate resuscitation, while 60% misclassified low scores. Additionally, 60% incorrectly believed that the first APGAR assessment is performed immediately at birth instead of at 1 minute. Knowledge regarding the structure of the APGAR score was high, with 93.3% correctly identifying its five parameters and their scoring. Nurses demonstrated strong understanding of individual parameters, particularly respiration, heart rate, muscle tone, reflex irritability, and skin color.

CONCLUSION: Nurses in the nursery and NICU demonstrated generally good knowledge of the APGAR scoring system and its components; however, gaps exist in interpreting critically low scores and understanding the correct timing of assessment.

INTRODUCTION

The Apgar score provides a standardized and practical method to report an infant's condition immediately after birth and to assess their response to resuscitation if necessary. It is important to note that an Apgar score assigned to a baby during resuscitation differs from one given to a baby who is breathing spontaneously. To address this, the American Academy of Pediatrics and the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists recommend a comprehensive Apgar scoring form that considers simultaneous resuscitation and management (1). Historically, in the United States during the 19th century, childbirth was primarily a family-centered event, assisted by midwives and female relatives in the home. Women increasingly sought the involvement of physicians with the hope of reducing pain and improving safety during labor and delivery. Over time, childbirth shifted from the home to hospital settings, reflecting the growing medicalization of delivery. Between 1935 and 1960, the proportion of hospital births increased dramatically, from 36.9% to 96% (2). In the hospital, women were exposed to new procedures including, cesarean birth, episiotomies, forceps-assisted birth as well as,

and anesthesia. Following delivery, obstetricians attended to the mother by carrying out techniques like episiotomies or mending tears, while paying no attention to the infants who were dejected from the maternal anesthetic (3). In the late 1940s, the newborn mortality rate was 20.5 per 1,000 live births, when Dr. Apgar started employment as an anesthesiologist at birth. Approximately 10 of the 20 neonates decreased during the first 24 hours, with the 3 crucial reasons for mortality being, birth traumas, and immaturity (3.9 neonates/1,000 live birth), postnatal hypoxia and atelectasis.(4) In 1952, Dr. Virginia Apgar developed a grading system to provide a rapid assessment of a newborn's clinical status at one minute of age and to determine the urgency of establishing respiration. She later published a follow-up report with a larger patient cohort, which helped validate the scoring system for consistent evaluation after delivery. The Apgar score comprises five components: (1) heart rate, (2) color, (3) reflex irritability, (4) respiration, and (5) muscle tone. Each component is assigned a score of 0, 1, or 2, with higher scores indicating better neonatal condition.

APGAR SCORING SYSTEM

	0 Points	1 Point	2 Points	Points totaled
Activity (muscle tone)	Absent	Arms and legs flexed	Active movement	
Pulse	Absent	Below 100 bpm	Over 100 bpm	
Grimace (reflex irritability)	Flaccid	Some flexion of Extremities	Active motion (sneeze, cough, pull away)	
Appearance (skin color)	Blue, pale	Body pink, Extremities blue	Completely pink	
Respiration	Absent	Slow, irregular	Vigorous cry	

Severely depressed	0-3
Moderately depressed	4-6
Excellent condition	7-10

Table: APGAR Score Parameters

<https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.bila.ca%2Fwhats-an-apgar-score-and-why-is-it-important-to-my->

As a result, the Apgar score evaluates clinical indicators of neonatal suffering, including hypotonia, cyanosis or pallor, bradycardia, gasping breathing, apnea, and a reduced reflex reaction to stimulus. The result is informed for infants with a score below 7.3 at 5-minute intervals until 20 minutes and for all newborns at 1 and 5 minutes after birth (1). The hospitalization of a newborn in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit usually causes significant suffering for the family members and especially to the mother. There is a chance of NICU abuse because of augmented NICU admissions, rising gestational ages, rising birth weights, and progressively reducing disease severity. When a newborn is admitted to the NICU, the mother and other family members frequently tolerate a significant deal of hardship. (5) Algamel, Elhawary, Amin, and Abd Elmenem's 2020 study found that 26.7% of term newborns are admitted to the neonatal (NICU) each year in

Egypt. In 2017, 2.5 million of her babies died all throughout the world. (6) The number of infant mortalities in 2019 was 2.4 million, or 6,700 day-to-day. Almost 1/3 of neonatal deaths occur within the first day of lifespan, and approximately three-quarters arise within the first week. (7) 73% of neonatal expiries occur during the first week of a lifetime, creating this a critical period (8).

An operational indicator of the response to resuscitation is the Apgar score at 5 min, and more definitely, the difference in the assessment from 1 to 5 minutes (1). Since the start of time, individuals have imagined resuscitation as the facility to bring the seemingly dead back to life. The newborn initial years can be very significant. An infant is creating the abrupt alteration from the uterus of the mother to the extra uterine surroundings at this moment. However it is recurrently possible to foretell when an infant can need resuscitation, these circumstances can

nonetheless occur unexpectedly and in settings that do not frequently deal with neonatal intensive care (9).

The Apgar score of 7 to 10 at 5min is measured as encouraging, a score of 4 to 6 is reflected as slightly abnormal, and a score of 0 to 3 is measured as low in term and late-preterm infants, according to the Neurologic Outcome report and Neonatal Encephalopathy. According to that article, a nonspecific symptom of a disease that "an Apgar score of 0 to 3 at 5 minutes or longer may be one of the first indications of encephalopathy". However, a constantly low Apgar score by itself is not a dependable marker of intrapartum compromise (1). Infants are predominantly vulnerable population during the newborn period while they complete several physiological adaptations essential for life outside the mother's uterus. However, there are significant rates of mortality morbidity during this time. (10) (11). Neonatal mortality is defined as the death of neonates within the first 28 days of life. Almost one million will die within the first 24 hours and 2 million newborns will die during the next seven days after delivery. Birth Asphyxia is a prolonged medical disorder that causes several morbidities and physical injury to newborns owing to a lack of oxygen. According to the World Health Organization birth asphyxia rank it as 3rd leading cause of neonatal mortality. (12) Birth asphyxia is the primary cause of newborn mortality it accounts for 29% of all deaths in the state and Asphyxia can result from a variety of factors, including prolonged delivery, placenta abruption, hypoxemia, cord prolapse, and infections in both the infant and mother. In Kenya gestational age fewer than 37 weeks known as prematurity, is the third main cause of birth asphyxia. (1) A neurological condition known as birth asphyxia is considered by a declined Apgar score at 1 and 5 minutes, insufficient oxygen intake, arterial PH, and incompetence to endure spontaneous

respiration at delivery. (12) The Apgar score is an organized method that includes an identical risk assessment scoring system to assess the infant's status objectively and to rapidly interpret the response to resuscitation to progress the newborn's chances of survival in the abrupt postpartum period. (13) (14) The newborn experiences a significant complication during birth as they transition from fetal to neonatal life. The most crucial time for an infant's continual development and growth is the first few hours after birth, and the newborn's outcome is largely determined by the quality of care received.(15)

AIM AND OBJECTIVE:

To evaluate the knowledge of nurses regarding the APGAR score in nurseries and neonatal intensive care units at tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted at tertiary care hospitals in Peshawar, including Khyber Teaching Hospital, and Lady Reading Hospital, all of which have well-established nurseries, NICUs, and trained nursing staff. The research was carried out from July 2025 to September 2025. A descriptive cross-sectional design was used to assess the knowledge of nurses regarding the APGAR score in nursery and neonatal intensive care unit settings. The study population consisted of registered nurses working in nurseries or NICUs with a minimum of six months of experience in pediatric or neonatal care and who were willing to participate. Nurses who were not employed in nursery or NICU settings, nursing students or trainees without formal qualifications, those with less than six months of relevant experience, and those who declined consent were excluded. A non-probability convenience sampling technique was applied. The sample size was calculated to be 60 using an online sample size

calculator, considering a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, and an assumed population

(Agree, Neutral, Disagree) were coded numerically and analyzed to identify trends and gaps in nurses' knowledge.

Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	12	20.0
	Female	48	80.0
Years of Experience	Less than 1 year	12	20.0
	1-3 years	12	20.0
	4-6 years	24	40.0
	More than 6 years	12	20.0
Area of Work	Nursery	24	40.0
	NICU	36	60.0

RESULT

A total of 60 nurses participated in the study. Regarding gender distribution, the majority were female (48, 80%), while male nurses constituted 12 (20%) of the sample. Regarding the area of work, 36 (60%) nurses were working in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU), while 24 (40%) were working in the Nursery. This data indicates that the sample was predominantly female, with a substantial proportion having moderate experience (4-6 years). Additionally, more nurses were employed in the NICU compared to the Nursery, reflecting the specialized staffing distribution in tertiary care hospitals

proportion of 50%. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of two sections: general knowledge of the APGAR score and specific scoring criteria for each of its five components (respirations, heart rate, muscle tone, reflex response, and skin color). Nurses were approached after obtaining permission from nursing supervisors, informed about the purpose of the study, assured of confidentiality, and provided with written questionnaires along with instructions for completion. Completed questionnaires were checked for completeness before data entry. Data was analyzed using statistical software (e.g., SPSS). Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize demographic characteristics and responses to questionnaire items. Knowledge-related responses in both sections were evaluated to determine overall understanding of the APGAR score and its clinical application. Likert-scale responses

Table 3.1 Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Figure 3.1: Years of Experience

though some misconceptions remain regarding

In terms of professional experience, most participants had 4-6 years of experience (24, 40%), followed by less than 1 year (12, 20%), 1-3 years (12, 20%), and more than 6 years (12, 20%).

the interpretation of low APGAR scores.

Table 3.2: Knowledge of Nurses Regarding APGAR Score

KNOWLEDGE OF NURSES ABOUT THE APGAR SCORE

Regarding the knowledge of nurses about the APGAR score, the majority of participants (48, 80%) correctly identified that the APGAR score assesses the newborn’s immediate health status at the 1st minute after birth, while 12 (20%) incorrectly believed it assesses maternal health. When asked about the interpretation of an APGAR score of 2 at 1 minute, 24 (40%) correctly categorized it as severe asphyxia requiring immediate resuscitation, whereas 24 (40%) considered it moderate asphyxia and 12 (20%) perceived it as mild asphyxia. Additionally, all participants (60, 100%) correctly identified that the primary purpose of the APGAR score is to assess the immediate clinical status of the newborn. These findings indicate a generally good level of knowledge,

Question	Response Category	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
What does the APGAR score assess at 1 minute?	Newborn’s immediate health status	48	80.0
	Maternal health	12	20.0
A newborn with APGAR score of 2 at 1 minute is considered:	Mild asphyxia	12	20.0
	Severe asphyxia, needs	24	40.0

	immediate resuscitation		
	Moderate asphyxia, monitor only	24	40.0
Primary purpose of the APGAR score:	To assess the immediate clinical status of the newborn	60	100.0

A majority of the participants (60%) incorrectly believed that the first APGAR assessment is performed immediately at birth, while 40% correctly identified that it is assessed 1 minute after birth. Regarding the timing of APGAR scoring, 95% agreed that the APGAR score is an objective method of assessing the newborn's condition; however, a small proportion expressed neutrality (1.7%) or disagreement (3.3%). Most participants (78.3%) acknowledged that the APGAR score is an important tool for evaluating the newborn's clinical status and response to resuscitation, while 21.7% were neutral, indicating some uncertainty. Knowledge about the structure of the score was strong, with 93.3% correctly agreeing that the APGAR score comprises five parameters each rated from 0 to 2, while only a small fraction was neutral (5%) or disagreed (1.7%).

Table 3.3: Knowledge Regarding APGAR Score

Question / Response Options	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
1. When is the 1st APGAR score			

typically assessed?			
At birth	36	60.0	60.0
1 minute after birth	24	40.0	40.0
2. The APGAR score is an objective method of quantifying the newborn's condition at 1, 3, and 10 minutes after birth.			
Agree	57	95.0	95.0
Neutral	1	1.7	1.7
Disagree	2	3.3	3.3
3. The APGAR score is a significant tool for interpreting the newborn's clinical status and response to resuscitation .			
Agree	47	78.3	78.3
Neutral	13	21.7	21.7
4. The APGAR score consists of five parameters; each score is from 0 to 2.			

Agree	56	93.3	93.3
Neutral	3	5.0	5.0
Disagree	1	1.7	1.7
Total	60	100.0	100.0

KNOWLEDGE REGARDING THE APGAR SCORE PARAMETERS

The assessment of nurses’ knowledge regarding the APGAR score parameters demonstrated a high level of understanding across all five components. For the respiration parameter, 80% correctly identified a strong cry as the best indicator of adequate respiratory effort. Similarly, knowledge of heart rate assessment was strong, as 90% selected a heart rate above 100 bpm, which corresponds to the optimal APGAR score. Muscle tone was also well recognized, with 93.3% identifying active movement as the correct response, while only a very small number selected limp (1.7%) or some flexion (5%). Reflex irritability was accurately identified by most participants, with 93.3% choosing vigorous cry as the highest score. Regarding skin color, 80% chose normal pink coloration as the best indicator of neonatal well-being, while 20% selected pink body with blue extremities. Overall, these results indicate that nurses working in the nursery and NICU have strong knowledge of individual APGAR score parameters, reflecting good clinical competence in newborn assessment.

Table 3.4: APGAR Parameter Scores

APGAR Parameter	Category	Frequency (n=60)	Percent (%)
Respiration	Weak cry	12	20.0
	Strong cry	48	80.0
Heart Rate	<100 bpm	6	10.0
	>100 bpm	54	90.0

Muscle Tone	Limp	1	1.7
	Some flexions	3	5.0
	Active	56	93.3
Reflex Response	No response	1	1.7
	Grimace	3	5.0
	Vigorous cry	56	93.3
Skin Color	Body pink/blue extremities	12	20.0
	Normal pink	48	80.0

DISCUSSION

The present study assessed the knowledge of nurses working in the Nursery and Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of tertiary care hospitals regarding the APGAR score, its purpose, interpretation, and component parameters. Overall, the findings indicate that nurses possess a generally good level of knowledge; however, certain gaps persist, particularly in the interpretation of critically low APGAR scores and the correct timing of assessment. These results align with trends reported in national and international literature.

In the present study, most of the nurses correctly acknowledged that APGAR score evaluates the immediate health status of the newborn at 1st minute of birth. The findings of Shrestha et al. (2019) reflect the current finding as they found that neonatal nurses had good awareness regarding purpose of APGAR score. Nurses working in neonatal settings commonly understand that APGAR scoring is important for determining the need for resuscitation, found Singh and Thomas (2021) similarly. Yet,

it was discovered in the present research that one-fifth (20%) of the participants erroneously marked that the APGAR score assesses mother health. Like the findings of Gadappa et al (2018) who reported presence of gaps in basic APGAR knowledge among nursing staff in

India, professionals need to continue revisiting the original vital concepts. A notable finding of this study was that 60% of nurses incorrectly believed that the first APGAR score is assessed immediately at birth rather than at 1 minute. This gap in knowledge mirrors the findings of Al-Yaseen et al. (2017) and Naz & Sultana (2020), who also reported confusion among nurses regarding the timing of APGAR assessments. Such misunderstandings have practical implications, as incorrect timing can affect the accuracy of neonatal evaluation and delay urgent interventions. Therefore, this area remains an important focus for neonatal training programs globally.

Responses of participants to the low scores also differed. Though 40% of them recognized APGAR score 2 at one minute as severe asphyxia requiring resuscitation, the remaining 60% did not. Similar results were found by Khan et al. (2018) in Pakistan, where majority of the nurses were aware of the APGAR score but faced difficulties in correctly interpreting the critically low score. Mekonnen et al. (2020) noted that neonatal care providers in Ethiopia misinterpreted low scores in a similar fashion. The findings indicate that while general APGAR knowledge is adequate, specific interpretative skills still require strengthening.

Knowledge regarding the structure and components of the APGAR score was strong in this study, with 93.3% correctly identifying that the score consists of five parameters rated from 0 to 2. This finding is supported by studies conducted by Borah et al. (2021) and Yadav et al. (2020), which also reported high awareness among NICU nurses regarding the five components: respiration, heart rate, muscle

tone, reflex irritability, and skin color. Similarly, in the present study, most nurses demonstrated excellent understanding of these parameters, particularly in identifying strong cry, heart rate >100 bpm, active muscle tone, vigorous cry, and normal pink color as the highest-scoring indicators. These results reflect a high level of clinical competence among neonatal nurses in tertiary care hospitals.

This research study's demographic findings are similar to those of other studies observing neonatal units, moderate experience and primarily female. In Pakistan, Rafiq et al. (2019) and Musa et al. (2022) reported that the nursing staff in Saudi NICU were mainly female-dominated and having moderate years of experience which is likely to be contributing to better familiarity with the assessment of the newborn APGAR score.

CONCLUSION

The study assessed the knowledge of nurses working in the Nursery and Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) regarding the APGAR score, its parameters, and interpretation. The results indicate that nurses generally possess a good understanding of the APGAR score's purpose, structure, and the scoring of individual parameters such as respiration, heart rate, muscle tone, reflex response, and skin color. Most participants could correctly identify the clinical significance of normal scores and the components of the APGAR scoring system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

REGULAR TRAINING PROGRAMS:

Conduct periodic workshops and refresher courses for nurses focused on APGAR scoring, with special emphasis on the interpretation of low scores and correct timing of assessments.

SIMULATION-BASED LEARNING:

Implement simulation exercises in neonatal care units to provide hands-on experience in assessing newborns and interpreting APGAR scores accurately.

STANDARDIZED PROTOCOLS: Develop and enforce standardized guidelines and checklists for APGAR scoring in both Nursery and NICU settings to minimize errors and enhance consistency.

CONTINUING EDUCATION: Encourage continuing professional development and mandatory competency assessments for all nurses working in neonatal care units.

FURTHER RESEARCH: Conduct multicenter studies to explore the correlation between nurses' knowledge of APGAR scoring and actual clinical performance during neonatal resuscitation.

REFERENCES

- Al-Wassia H, Saber M. Admission of term infants to the neonatal intensive care unit in a Saudi tertiary teaching hospital: cumulative incidence and risk factors. *Ann Saudi Med.* 2017;37(6):420–4.
- Devitt N. The Transition from Home to Hospital Birth in the United States, 1930–1960. *Birth.*
- Devitt N. The Transition from Home to Hospital Birth in the United States, 1930–1960. *Birth.* 1977;4(2):47–58.
- Elghandour M, Hassan R, Ebrahim G. Assess Nurses' Knowledge and Practices about Immediate Care Bundle Protocol for Neonates. *Mansoura Nurs J.* 2023;10(2):213–25.
- Ersdal H, Mdoe P, Mduma E, Moshiri R, Guga G, Kvaløy JT, et al. “Safer Births Bundle of Care” Implementation and Perinatal Impact at 30 Hospitals in Tanzania—Halfway Evaluation. *Children.* 2023;10(2):1–18.
- Haidari ES, Lee HC, Illuzzi JL, Phibbs CS, Lin H, Xu X. Hospital variation in admissions to neonatal intensive care units by diagnosis severity and category. *J Perinatol.*
- Haidari ES, Lee HC, Illuzzi JL, Phibbs CS, Lin H, Xu X. Hospital variation in admissions to neonatal intensive care units by diagnosis severity and category. *J Perinatol.* 2021;41(3):468–77.
- Högberg U. The World Health Report 2005: “Make every mother and child count” – including Africans. *Scand J Public Health.* 2005;33(6):409–11.
- Joseph T, Science MOF. Resuscitation Protocol for Staff Nurses of a Selected Hospital in Mangalore ”
- Kattwinkel J, Perlman JM, Aziz K, Colby C, Fairchild K, Gallagher J, et al. Special Report - Neonatal resuscitation: 2010 American Heart Association guidelines for cardiopulmonary resuscitation and emergency cardiovascular care. *Pediatrics.* 2010;126(5).
- Muhe LM, McClure EM, Nigussie AK, Mekasha A, Worku B, Worku A, et al. Major causes of death in preterm infants in selected hospitals in Ethiopia (SIP): a prospective, cross-sectional, observational study. *Lancet Glob Heal.* 2019;7(8):e1130–8.
- Noor S, Praveen K, Hussain M, Afzal M, Gilani SA. Observational Study on Standard Practices of Nurses in Birth Asphyxia Management at a Tertiary Care Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. *Natl J Heal Sci.* 2020;5(1):24–9.
- Rahman F, Hossain M, Yasmin R. The importance of the APGAR score in neonatal outcome assessments. *Glob J Neonatol.* 2017;6(2):98–104.
- Rodríguez, Velastequí M. No Title. 2019;1–23.
- Smith, Butterfield PM. Foundations of Pediatrics. Virginia Apgar (1909-1974). *Adv Pediatr.* 2012;59(1)
- Smith, Butterfield PM. Foundations of Pediatrics. Virginia Apgar (1909-1974). *Adv Pediatr.* 2012;59(1):1–7.
- Watterberg KL, Aucott S, Benitz WE, Cummings JJ, Eichenwald EC, Goldsmith J, et al. The apgar score. *Pediatrics.* 2015;136(4):819–22.